

Dynamics of adsorption of lead from aqueous solution by hydrolyzed poly-methyl methacrylate

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Abstract : In present work hydrolyzed poly-methyl methacrylate (HPMMA) was tested for the removal of lead from aqueous solution. Effect of various parameters such as pH, adsorbent dose, initial Pb ion concentration, contact time and temperature on adsorption of Pb^{II} onto HPMMA was investigated. Equilibrium studies show that the adsorption follows both the Langmuir and Freundlich isotherm models. Kinetic and thermodynamic studies were performed on different initial concentration of Pb^{II} ion. Kinetic studies show that the adsorption follows pseudo-second order kinetics and intraparticle diffusion model. Negative values of Gibb's free energy change (ΔG°) show that the adsorption was feasible and spontaneous and negative values of enthalpy change (ΔH°) confirm exothermic adsorption.

Keywords : Adsorption, equilibrium, lead, hydrolyzed poly-methyl methacrylate, intraparticle diffusion, thermodynamics.

Introduction

The heavy metal pollution is of great concern because of their high toxicity and other adverse effects on human health. The release of heavy metals from many industrial processes leads to an increase the concentration of heavy metals in aquatic system, which causes serious environmental problems in view of human health. Among the different heavy metals, lead is one of the common and most toxic pollutants released into the natural waters from various industrial activities such as metal plating, oil refining and battery manufacturing. Lead has been found to be acute toxic to human beings when present in high amounts (e.g. > 15 $\mu\text{g/L}$ in drinking water)¹. Lead can cause acute adverse effects on the liver, kidney and reproductive system, basic cellular processes and brain functions. Hence it is necessary to remove lead from water at least below the regulatory level.

Various processes have been proposed for the removal of lead from aqueous solution. The important ones are adsorption², ion exchange³, photocatalysis⁴, floatation, hyperfiltration, chemical precipitation, reverse osmosis etc. Among these the adsorption process is found to be quite suitable, cheap and effective for the removal of lead from aqueous solution. A number of adsorbents includ-

ing clay⁵, zeolite⁶, biosorbent⁷⁻⁹, agricultural wastes¹⁰, organic/inorganic composite¹¹ and alumina¹² have been tried for the removal of lead from aquatic system.

Poly-methyl methacrylate (PMMA) is a transparent thermoplastic and synthetic polymer of methyl methacrylate. It is a low cost material used for several purposes such as in medical, optics, semiconductor, paints etc. The acid hydrolysis of PMMA surface was done to get free carboxylic acid groups on its surface for adsorption. This paper presents results on the ability of hydrolyzed poly-methyl methacrylate (HPMMA) to effective removal of lead from aqueous solutions.

Results and discussion

FT-IR study :

The FT-IR spectra of PMMA and HPMMA were recorded by FTLA2000 spectrophotometer using KBr disc method. Spectra of PMMA shows a band at 1739 cm^{-1} was due to C=O stretching of ester group. Appearance of band at 3440 cm^{-1} appears to be a overtone band having frequency twice that of C=O stretching frequency. A band at 1242 cm^{-1} is due to C-O-C stretching. Band at 2951 and 2994 cm^{-1} are due to C-H stretching. The corresponding bending peak occurs at 1449 cm^{-1} . Spectra of

HPMMA shows a band at 1712 cm^{-1} which is due to C=O stretching of carboxylic group. Broad O-H stretching band occurs at $3100\text{--}3400\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The shifting of C=O stretching band from 1739 to 1720 cm^{-1} confirms hydrolysis of ester group of PMMA.

Influence of pH :

The influence of pH on adsorption of Pb^{II} ion was studied over the pH range 2–6. For this 10 mg/L Pb^{II} solution containing 5 g/L adsorbent was used and temperature was maintained 303 K and the contact time was kept 60 min . Fig. 1 shows that the adsorption of Pb^{II} ion on HPMMA was increased from 34 to 90% with increasing pH from 2 to 6 due to increasing availability of anionic site ($-\text{COO}^-$) for adsorption of Pb^{II} . At lower pH values, hydrogen ion competes with Pb^{II} ion and most of the carboxyl of adsorbent exists in the form of $-\text{COOH}$, which reduce the adsorbed amounts for Pb^{II} ion. At higher pH values, more $-\text{COO}^-$ occur, which may enhance electrostatic attraction and the adsorption capacity of adsorbent for Pb^{II} ion. Further increase in pH causes precipitation of Pb^{II} due to formation of hydroxide, so the pH higher than 6 was avoided.

Fig. 1. Influence of pH on adsorption of Pb^{II} on HPMMA.

Effect of adsorbent dose :

The effect of adsorbent dose on adsorption was studied using different adsorbent dosage in the range of 1 to 6 g/L keeping the initial Pb^{II} concentration of at 10 mg/L while pH was fixed at 6, temperature at 303 K with contact time 60 min . Fig. 2 shows that on increasing adsorbent dose from 1 to 5 g/L the adsorption of Pb^{II} on HPMMA increases from 20 to 90%. The increase is due to the greater availability of the adsorption binding sites.

Fig. 2. Effect of adsorbent dose on adsorption of Pb^{II} on HPMMA

Further increase of adsorbent dose of HPMMA did not cause any significant change because equilibrium was achieved between solid and solution phase.

Effect of initial Pb^{II} ion concentration and contact time :

To observe the effect of initial Pb^{II} concentration and contact time on adsorption, the experiments were conducted over the wide range of initial Pb^{II} ion concentration ($5\text{--}25\text{ mg/L}$) at constant adsorbent dose (5 g/L), pH (6) and temperature (303 K). The % removal of Pb^{II} decreases from 92 to 77% with increasing Pb^{II} initial concentration from 5 to 25 mg/L . The decrease in adsorption of Pb^{II} is due to lesser availability of adsorption site. Fig. 3 shows that the rates of adsorption was very fast in first 10 min which decreases with increase of time and after 60 min equilibrium were achieved.

Adsorption isotherm :

The analysis of the sorption process requires the relevant adsorption equilibria for better understanding the

Fig. 3. Effect of initial dye concentration and contact time on adsorption of Pb^{II} on HPMMA.

adsorption process. Sorption equilibrium describes the nature of adsorbate-adsorbent interaction. In the present study the equilibrium data were analyzed using the Langmuir and Freundlich isotherms.

Langmuir isotherm model :

The saturated monolayer isotherm can be represented as :

$$q_e = Q_m b C_e / (1 + b C_e) \tag{1}$$

The linearized forms of eq. (1) can be written as follows¹³ :

$$C_e / q_e = 1 / b Q_m + C_e / Q_m \tag{2}$$

where q_e is the adsorption density (mg/g) at equilibrium of Pb^{II}, C_e is the equilibrium concentration (mg/L) of the Pb^{II} in solution, Q_m is the monolayer adsorption capacity (mg/g) and b is the Langmuir constant (L/mg) related to the free energy of adsorption. The values of Q_m and b were calculated from the slopes ($1/Q_m$) and intercepts ($1/bQ_m$) of the linear plots of C_e/q_e vs C_e (Fig. 4) and given in Table 1. Linear plots of C_e/q_e vs C_e show that the adsorption isotherm of Pb^{II} on HPMMA follows the Langmuir isotherm model at all three temperatures (303, 313 and 323 K). Higher value of Q_m at 303 K indicates that the higher adsorption capacity of HPMMA at lower temperature.

Fig. 4. The Langmuir plots for the adsorption of Pb^{II} on HPMMA.

Freundlich isotherm model :

Freundlich isotherm can be expressed as follows¹⁴ :

$$q_e = K_f C_e^{1/n} \tag{3}$$

The linearized forms of eq. (3) can be written as follows :

$$\ln q_e = \ln K_f + (1/n) \ln C_e \tag{4}$$

where K_f and n are Freundlich constants related to sorption capacity [$\text{mg g}^{-1} (\text{mg L}^{-1})^{-1/n}$] and sorption intensity of adsorbents. The values of the K_f and n were calculated from the intercepts ($\ln K_f$) and slopes ($1/n$) of the plots $\ln q_e$ vs $\ln C_e$ (Fig. 5) and presented in Table 1. Linear plots of $\ln q_e$ vs $\ln C_e$ show that the adsorption isotherm of Pb^{II} on HPMMA also fitted well in the Freundlich isotherm model. The values of $n > 1$ indicates favourable adsorption conditions^{15,16}.

Fig. 5. The Freundlich plots for the adsorption of Pb^{II} on HPMMA.

Adsorption kinetics :

Several kinetic models have been proposed to clarify the mechanism of a solute sorption from aqueous solution onto an adsorbent. The rate constant of adsorption was determined from the pseudo-first order rate expression¹⁷ (eq. (5)) given by Lagergren :

$$\ln (q_e - q_t) = \ln (q_e - k_1 t) \tag{5}$$

where q_e and q_t are the amount of Pb^{II} adsorbed at equi-

Table 1. Isotherm parameters for Pb^{II} adsorption on HPMMA

Temp. (K)	Langmuir isotherm parameters			Freundlich isotherm parameters		
	Q_{max}	b	R^2	K_f	n	R^2
303	5.12	0.58	0.999	1.71	1.84	0.967
313	4.71	0.31	1.000	1.13	1.77	0.979
323	3.93	0.21	0.999	0.76	1.76	0.979

librium and at time t (mg/g) respectively and k_1 (min^{-1}) is rate constant of adsorption. The values of k_1 and q_e^{cal} were calculated from the slopes ($-k_1$) and intercepts ($\ln q_e$) of the plots of $\ln(q_e - q_t)$ vs t (Fig. 6) respectively (Table 2).

Fig. 6. Pseudo-first order kinetics plots for adsorption of Pb^{II} on HPMMA (adsorbent dose : 5 g/L; pH : 6; Temperature : 303 K).

The pseudo-second order sorption kinetics¹⁷ may be written as follows :

$$t/q_t = 1/k_2 q_e^2 + t/q_e \quad (6)$$

where k_2 is the rate constant of sorption (g/mg min), q_e and q_t are the amount of Pb^{II} adsorbed at equilibrium and at time t (mg/g) respectively. The values of k_2 and q_e^{cal} were calculated from the intercepts ($1/k_2 q_e^2$) and slopes ($1/q_e$) of the plots of t/q_t vs t (Fig. 7) respectively (Table 2).

From Table 2 it is clear that the values of regression correlation coefficient (R^2) are closer to 1 and the values of q_e^{cal} and q_e^{exp} are almost equal for pseudo-second order kinetic model. Therefore it can be concluded that in present case the adsorption of Pb^{II} onto HPMMA follows pseudo-second order kinetic model.

The mechanism of adsorption can be explained by

Fig. 7. Pseudo-second order kinetics plots for adsorption of Pb^{II} on HPMMA (adsorbent dose : 5 g/L; pH : 6; Temperature : 303 K).

intraparticle diffusion model¹⁸ which can be expressed as follows :

$$q_t = k_i t^{0.5} + C \quad (7)$$

where k_i is the intraparticle diffusion constant ($\text{mg/g min}^{0.5}$) and the intercept (C) reflects the boundary layer effect. The values of k_i were calculated from slopes (k_i) of the plots of q_t vs $t^{0.5}$ (Fig. 8) and presented in Table 2. Table 2 shows that the rate constant for intraparticle diffusion

Fig. 8. Intraparticle diffusion plots for the adsorption of Pb^{II} from aqueous solution on HPMMA (adsorbent dose : 5 g/L; pH : 6; Temperature : 303 K).

Table 2. Kinetic parameters for Pb^{II} adsorption on HPMMA

Initial Pb^{II} concentration (mg/L)	q_e^{exp}	Pseudo-first order			Pseudo-second order			Intraparticle diffusion		
		q_e^{cal}	k_1	R^2	q_e^{cal}	k_2	R^2	k_i	C	R^2
5	0.90	0.64	0.053	0.946	0.93	0.314	0.990	0.058	0.46	0.985
10	1.80	1.26	0.055	0.951	1.83	0.169	0.991	0.111	0.94	0.983
15	2.64	3.30	0.069	0.967	2.68	0.103	0.989	0.181	1.24	0.964
20	3.36	2.55	0.060	0.968	3.47	0.076	0.990	0.251	1.48	0.943
25	3.88	1.83	0.052	0.934	4.03	0.068	0.991	0.278	1.83	0.967

(k_i) increased with increasing initial Pb^{II} concentration. The driving force of diffusion is very important for adsorption processes. The increase of the initial Pb^{II} concentration results in an increase of the driving force, which will increase the diffusion rate of Pb^{II} ¹⁹. Fig. 8 shows that the lines of plots are not passing through the origin. Table 2 shows that the values of C increase with increase in initial concentration of Pb^{II} . Larger the value of C , greater is the contribution of the surface sorption in the rate-limiting step, which confirms the presence of both surface adsorption and intraparticle diffusion.

Thermodynamic study :

To observe the effect of temperature on the adsorption of Pb^{II} on HPMMA, experiments were conducted at three different temperatures 303, 313 and 323 K. It was observed that the adsorption decreases with increasing temperature, which indicates a low temperature favours Pb^{II} removal by sorption onto the HPMMA. This may be due to a tendency for the Pb^{II} molecules to escape from the solid phase to the bulk phase with an increase in temperature of the solution. A similar observation was also reported in the study on the sorption of Pb onto modified and unmodified kaolinite clay²¹.

Thermodynamic parameters such as enthalpy (ΔH°), entropy (ΔS°) and Gibb's free energy (ΔG°) were determined by eqs. (8)²² and (9).

$$\ln (q_e m / C_e) = \Delta S^\circ / R - \Delta H^\circ / RT \quad (8)$$

$$\Delta G^\circ = \Delta H^\circ - T\Delta S^\circ \quad (9)$$

where m is the adsorbent dose (mg/L), C_e is the equilibrium concentration (mg/L) of the Pb^{II} in solution and $q_e m$ is the solid-phase concentration (mg/L) at equilibrium. R is the gas constant (8.314 J/mol/K) and T is the temperature (K). ΔH° , ΔS° and ΔG° are changes in enthalpy (J/mol), entropy (J/mol/K) and Gibb's free energy (J/mol), respectively.

The values of ΔH° and ΔS° were determined from the slope ($-\Delta H^\circ / R$) and the intercept ($\Delta S^\circ / R$) of the plots of $\ln (q_e m / C_e)$ vs $1/T$ (Fig. 9). The ΔG° values were calculated by using eq. (9). The values of thermodynamic parameters are presented in Table 3. Negative values of ΔG° indicate that the adsorption process is feasible and spontaneous in nature. Negative values of ΔH° suggest the exothermic nature of adsorption and the negative value of ΔS° described the decrease in randomness at the ad-

Fig. 9. The plots of $\ln (q_e m / C_e)$ vs $1/T$ for adsorption of Pb^{II} on HPMMA (adsorbent dose : 5 g/L; pH : 6; contact time 60 min).

Table 3. Thermodynamic parameters for Pb^{II} adsorption on HPMMA

Initial Pb^{II} concentration (mg/L)	ΔH° (kJ/mol)	ΔS° (J/mol/K)	ΔG° (kJ/mol)		
			303 K	313 K	323 K
5	-49.717	-143.49	-6.240	-4.805	-3.370
10	-49.651	-145.32	-5.620	-4.193	-2.713
15	-50.773	-151.06	-5.002	-3.492	-1.994
20	-46.342	-139.25	-4.150	-2.757	-1.365
25	-38.044	-115.23	-3.130	-1.978	-0.825

sorbent-solution interface during the sorption. The ΔH° values obtained for adsorption of Pb^{II} on HPMMA are in the range of -38.04 to -49.71 kJ/mol, which indicates that the physical and chemical, both the adsorption mechanism was present in the sorption process.

Experimental

Adsorbent :

Poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) was obtained from Sigma Aldrich, India (average Mol. wt. 15000, powder) and was hydrolysed by procedure reported by Brown *et al.*²³. PMMA was sonicated for 10 min in a 50% aqueous 2-propanol solution and dried under a stream of nitrogen to clean and hydrate the polymer surface. The PMMA was then submerged in 3 M sulphuric acid at 60 °C for 20 min to have the following reaction.

The resulting material was rinsed with copious amounts of water, followed by rinsing with 2-propanol and dried in oven at 50 °C. The final material (HPMMA) was kept in desiccator for its use as an adsorbent.

Adsorption experiment :

Stock solution of Pb^{II} (1000 mg/L) was prepared by dissolving requisite amount of lead nitrate (Merck) into double distilled water from this a number of solutions with concentration of lead as 5, 10, 15, 20 and 25 mg L⁻¹ were prepared with appropriate dilution. The pH of all these solutions was maintained by adding 0.1 M HNO₃ or 0.1 M NaOH. 50 mL of Pb solution was taken in 150 mL conical flask and required amount of adsorbent was added into that. The resultant solution was stirred on magnetic stirrer (Remi) at the speed of 200 rpm. The adsorption was monitored by determining the concentration of Pb^{II} in solution by atomic absorption spectrophotometer (ECIL-4141).

Percentage of Pb^{II} adsorption and quantity of Pb^{II} adsorbed on adsorbent at the time of equilibrium (q_e) was calculated using eqs. (10) and (11) respectively.

$$\% \text{ adsorption} = (C_0 - C_e)/C_0 \times 100 \quad (10)$$

$$q_e = (C_0 - C_e) V/W \quad (11)$$

where C_0 and C_e are the initial and the equilibrium concentrations (mg/L) of Pb^{II} in solution, respectively, q_e is quantity of Pb^{II} adsorbed on the adsorbent at the time of equilibrium (mg/g), V is volume (L) of solution and W is weight of adsorbent (g) taken for experiment.

Batch experiments were carried out to determine the effects of pH, adsorbent dose, initial dye concentration, contact time and temperature by varying the parameter under study and keeping other parameters constant.

Conclusions :

The results of the study clearly demonstrate that HPMMA is a potential adsorbent for the removal of Pb^{II} from aqueous medium. And the optimum condition for the adsorption was found to be pH 6 and temperature 303 K. Equilibrium studies show that the adsorption Pb^{II} on to HPMMA followed the Langmuir and Freundlich isotherm models. Adsorption processes follow pseudo-second order kinetics, surface adsorption and intraparticle diffusion mechanism. The negative values of ΔH° and ΔG° indicate that the adsorption of Pb^{II} onto HPMMA was a thermodynamically feasible, spontaneous and exothermic process.

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